

Analyzing Methods Best Used In Translating Song *Swimming Pools (Drank)* – *Extended Version* by Kendrick Lamar

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ABSTRACT: This study analysed the most effective translation methods for Kendrick Lamar’s rap song “Swimming Pools (Drank) – Extended Version,” focusing on bridging linguistic and cultural gaps in song translation. Using Molina & Albir’s translation techniques as the theoretical framework, the research explored how the cultural nuances and lyrical complexity of rap music could be conveyed accurately in the target language. The qualitative approach involved a detailed examination of the song’s lyrics, considering both contextual and cultural factors, and applying selected techniques from the eighteen methods proposed by Molina & Albir. The findings highlighted that the most frequently used translation techniques were amplification, adaptation, substitution, and particularization, as these methods were essential for maintaining the original song’s stylistic elements, cultural essence, and semantic structure. The study aimed to provide insights for English and Tourism students, encouraging a deeper understanding of translation methods and fostering creative approaches for future translation projects. The results were expected to dispel misconceptions about Indonesian rap culture and served as a reference for translating culturally rich artistic expressions.

Keywords: *translation methods, Molina & Albir techniques, song translation, cultural adaptation, amplification*

INTRODUCTION

Language barriers or language difficulties make it difficult for individuals to exchange information, ideas, and opinions, which can result in misinterpretations and poor communication. This can be mitigated by the presence of translators who are competent in the language and culture of both countries (Buarqoub, 2019). Language hurdles can appear as major obstacles when people from different cultural backgrounds want to communicate. At this point, a translator's function as a cross-cultural mediator becomes essential. Cross-linguistic contact is facilitated by translators who translate spoken or written information between languages. To effectively communicate the message, this method requires a thorough comprehension of both the source and target languages in addition to cultural quirks. According to Smith (as cited in Cherouana, 2023), translators are essential in removing linguistic barriers and facilitating the sharing of knowledge, concepts, and cultural practices across various linguistic groups. In order to maintain the grammatical,

syntactical, and lexical standards of both the source and target languages, translators must guarantee the accurate translation of words, phrases, and sentences (García & Martinez, 2020, as cited in, Cherouana, 2023). For instance, while translating legal documents, a translator must faithfully translate legal terms and ideas from the Source Language (SL) to the Target Language (TL).

The entertainment world also experiences the language barrier. Song translations require qualified translators so that their products can impress and be understood by audiences who have a different language from them. Unfortunately, specialized learning for film and song translation is still rarely implemented, and some translators only translate according to their own intuition rather than theoretically (Chang, 2012). The music industries that strive to reach a global audience requires translators to take translations even more seriously in order to produce accurate and faithful translations of movies or songs that are accurate and truly appropriate so that the intentions of the music makers can be conveyed.

This translation needs a grounded perspective on one translation technique in order to qualify as theoretical. The source language (SL) refers to the language in which the original text or message is written. The target language (TL) is the language into which the text is translated. It represents the end product of the translation process. The translation method will be used in this report was proposed by Molina & Albir (2002), which consist of eighteen methods, including adaptation, borrowing, calque, amplification, description, compensation, linguistic amplification, linguistic compression, reduction, modulation, particularization, generalization, substitution, literal translation, transposition, established equivalent, discursive creation, and substitution.

This study chooses "Swimming Pools (Drank)" by Kendrick Lamar, an American hip-hop musician. The lead single off his major-label debut studio album "good kid, m.a.a.d city" by Top Dawg, Aftermath, and Interscope was released on July 31, 2012. Lamar co-wrote the song with

Tyler "T-Minus" Williams, who also served as its producer. Dr. Dre and Derek "Mixed Byali" Ali, the engineer for Top Dawg, mixed the song, which helped make Lamar a household name. After steadily rising up the chart, the song reached its highest position at number 17 on the US Billboard Hot 100 in its twelfth week of release. It started at number 100 on the Hot 100 and rose from numbers 55 and 32 to its highest position. Lamar also made his debut on the UK Singles Chart with "Swimming Pools (Drank)" at number 63 (Asianboyian, 2022.).

Several studies have been done related to song translation analysis. The first references were written by Wijaya, I.N.A, & Hadi, M.Z.P. (2024) entitled "Analysis of Translation Techniques in English Version of Nadin Amizah's 'Bertaut' Song Lyrics". This research focuses on analysing the techniques used in translating the song "Bertaut" by Nadin Amizah into English by Emma Heesters using the theory of Molina and Albir (2002). This research uses a qualitative descriptive method by highlighting several strategies such as adaptation, modulation, equivalence, amplification, transposition, reduction, and direct translation. This report proves that the Molina & Albir (2002) method used by Emma Heesters in translating song lyrics can convey the meaning and emotion of the original song lyrics while explaining the complexities involved in translating lyrics from Indonesian into English.

The second references were written by Rahmawati, A. A., Nababan, R. M., & Santosa, R. (2016). With English as the original language, this study attempts to examine how sexist expressions are translated in two books. The research identifies the types and characteristics of sexist language, the translation methods used, and how these methods affect the evaluation of the quality of the translated text, which includes accuracy and understandability. This research is focused on the translation product and uses a descriptive qualitative research design with an integrated case study. Documents chosen using the purposive sampling approach plus the outcomes of the conversation with the informant comprise the data source. According to the

research's summary, the results of using approaches to translate sexist expressions demonstrate a high degree of accuracy and acceptance in the translation.

The third references were by Mogi, C. A., Tulung, J. G., & Ranuntu, G. J. (2023). This study aims to classify the translation strategies used for songs in Indonesian dubbing in Moana movie. A descriptive qualitative design was used to answer the problem formulation with data sources of four songs from the English version of the movie Moana and the Indonesian dubbed version. From the analysed data, the translation of voiceover of Moana movie songs uses five strategies. Translation strategy metrical translation strategy dominates with 46% usage. Then, blank verse translation (23.8%), interpretive translation (11.9%), phonemic translation (11.1%), and finally literal translation with 7.1%. This research focuses on analysing eighteen translation techniques according to Molina & Albir (2002) that are appropriate for Kendrick Lamar's song "Swimming Pool (Drank) – Extended Version" in knowing the meaning and context of each line of its lyrics into Indonesian.

To fulfil the gap, this study formulates the following research question: what is the proper translation methods by Molina & Albir to be used for translating a song entitled "Swimming Pool (Drank)- Extended version by Kendrick Lamar"?

METHOD

The qualitative method was employed to explore the challenges people commonly face in understanding the intended meaning of songs. The focus is particularly on songs that carry cultural meanings. These songs often present difficulties in translation, as their meanings cannot be accepted by explicit or direct translation. Based on Basrowi and Suwandi (as cited in Malahati et al., 2023) through qualitative research, researchers can identify the subject and feel what the subject feels in everyday life. In qualitative research, the writer will understand the background

atmosphere and natural events in accordance with what is being studied. Each of these events is a unique object, because of its different contexts. Therefore, in reviewing the existing problems the author decided to use qualitative methods. The purpose of qualitative research is to master the situation by focusing on describing in detail and in-depth the portrait of a natural condition (natural setting), about what really happened according to what it is in the study field. Therefore, according to Yusanto (as cited in Malahati et al., 2023), qualitative research has various approaches, so that researchers can sort out various approaches to adjust the subject they want to research. In short, the qualitative method is a research method that looks at real problems that exist in everyday life, explained descriptively and it is a flexible method that can adjust according to the author's research.

The following procedures were used to examine the data gathered from the lyrics collecting and text analysis. A) Scanning: The writer analyses by listening and matching the song with the lyrics on genius.com to avoid writing errors in the form of typos and punctuation errors that can complicate the translation that the writer will do in the next stage. The song will be matched with the lyrics by verse per verse and will be reviewed so that there are no writing or inputting errors in Chapter 4 later. B) Gathering Data: In this stage the writer not only looks at the lyrics of the song to be translated but the writer also looks at the concept of the album and watch interview about the background of the artist which will be obtained from many webs' literature such as genius.com and youtube.com to add cultural and contextual insights brought in the song so as to minimize errors in translating. C) Translating: This stage is the most important one in this report as the author will translate the song using the translation method according to Molina & Albir (2002) by using the appropriate technique from eighteen existing techniques based on the context and culture brought to the song along with a detailed explanation of why the technique is appropriate for the lyrics that have been translated. D) Evaluating: The writer

provides the results of the translation to experts who are competent in the field to be reviewed and given input and responses to the translated results so that this report becomes a cohesive and reliable report.

RESULT

In order to clarify this report, the author determined the codes for the 18 translation methods by Molina and Albir (2002) shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Translation Methods Code

Number	Translation Methods	Codes
1	Adaptation	AD
2	Amplification	AP
3	Borrowing	BR
4	Calque	CL
5	Compensation	CP
6	Description	DS
7	Discursive Creation	DC
8	Established Equivalent	EQ
9	Generalization	GN
10	Linguistic Amplification	LA
11	Linguistic Compression	LC
12	Literal Translation	LT
13	Modulation	MO
14	Particularization	PT
15	Reduction	RD
16	Substitution	SB
17	Transposition	TP
18	Variation	VR

This section presents the findings of the analysis of translation methods applied in translating the lyrics of Kendrick Lamar's "Swimming Pools (Drank) – Extended Version" into Indonesian using Molina and Albir's (2002) translation techniques. The results are derived from a systematic comparison between the source language (English) lyrics and their target language (Indonesian) translations. Each lyric line was examined to identify the translation technique(s) employed, and the data were then categorized according to the eighteen techniques proposed by Molina and Albir. The findings are presented in the form

of coding tables to provide a clear and structured overview of the translation outcomes, without interpretative commentary, which is further elaborated in the subsequent discussion section.

Table 2. Translation Results

Source Language	Target Language	Translation Methods
Pour up (Drank)	<i>Tuang (minum)</i>	LT
Head shot (Drank)	<i>tertembak di kepala (minum)</i>	LT, AP
Sit down (Drank)	<i>Duduk (minum)</i>	LT
Stand up (Drank)	<i>Berdiri (minum)</i>	LT
Pass out (Drank)	<i>Pingsan (Tetap minum)</i>	LT, AP
Wake up (Drank)	<i>Bangun (minum)</i>	LT
Faded (Drank)	<i>Pudar (minum)</i>	LT
Now, I done grew up round some people	<i>Sekarang aku sudah muak besar di lingkungan orang-orang tertentu.</i>	AP, AD, PT
Livin' their life in bottles	<i>Yang menghabiskan hidupnya dengan minuman keras</i>	MO, AP, PT
Granddaddy had the golden flask	<i>Kakek memiliki botol kecil berwarna emas.</i>	MO, DS
Backstroke every day in Chicago	<i>Mabuk – mabuk setiap hari di Chicago</i>	AD, SB
Some people like the way it feels	<i>Beberapa orang menyukai bagaimana rasanya.</i>	LT
Some people wanna kill their sorrow	<i>Beberapa orang ingin menghilangkan kesedihan mereka.</i>	SB
Some people wanna fit in with the popular	<i>Beberapa orang ingin diterima oleh kelompok orang yang populer.</i>	AP
That was my problem	<i>Itulah masalahku</i>	LT
I was in a dark room, loud tunes	<i>Saya berada di ruangan gelap, dengan suara yang keras.</i>	LT, AP
Lookin' to make a vow soon	<i>Berencana untuk mengucapkan janji segera</i>	EQ
That "I'ma get fucked up"	<i>Bahwa "Aku akan mabuk berat"</i>	PT
Fillin' up my cup, I see the crowd mood	<i>Mengisi cangkirku, kulihat suasana kerumunan.</i>	LT
Changin' by the minute	<i>Berganti Setiap Menitnya</i>	LT
And the record on repeat	<i>Dan lagunya diputar berulang</i>	LT
Took a sip, then another sip	<i>Minum seteguk, lalu seteguk lagi.</i>	LT
Then somebody said to me	<i>Lalu seseorang berkata kepadaku</i>	LT

“Nigga, why you babysittin’ only two or three shots?”	“Bro, kenapa kamu Cuma main dua atau tiga sloki aja?”	AD
“I’m show you how to turn it up a notch”	”Aku akan tunjukkan caranya biar makin seru.”	MO
First, you get a swimming pool full of liquor, then you dive in it	Pertama-tama, kamu dapatkan sebuah kolam renang yang penuh dengan minuman beralkohol, lalu kamu menyelam ke dalamnya.	AP , LT
Pool full of liquor, then you dive in it	kolam renang yang penuh dengan minuman beralkohol, lalu kamu menyelam ke dalamnya.	AP , LT
Then, I wave a few bottles, then I watch ‘em all flock	Lalu, aku mengangkat beberapa botol, dan semua orang berkerumun.	SB, LC,
All the girls wanna play Baywatch	Semua cewek ingin bermain di Series Baywatch	AP
I got a swimming pool full of liquor and they dive in it	Aku memiliki kolam renang penuh dengan minuman keras dan mereka menyelam di dalamnya.	LT
Po-Pool full of liquor, I’m dive in it	Ko-Kolam penuh minuman keras, aku akan menyelam di dalamnya.	EQ, LT
Okay, now open your mind up and listen me, Kendrick	Oke, sekarang buka pikiranmu dan dengarkan aku, Kendrick.	LT
I am your conscience, if you do not hear me then you will be history, Kendrick	Akulah suara hatimu, jika kau tidak mendengarkanku, maka kau akan menjadi sejarah, Kendrick.	LT
I know that you’re nauseous right now and I’m hopin’ to lead you to victory, Kendrick	Aku tahu kamu merasa mual sekarang dan aku berharap bisa membawamu menuju kemenangan, Kendrick.	LT
If I take another one down, I’m drown in some poison, abusin’ my limit	Jika aku minum segelas lagi, aku akan tenggelam dalam racun,(alkohol), melampaui batasku.	PT, AP
I think that I’m feelin’ the vibe, I see the love in her eyes	Aku berpikir aku merasakan getarannya, kulihat cinta di matanya.	LT
I see the feelin’, the freedom is granted as soon as the damage of vodka arrived	Aku merasakan perasaannya, kebebasan itu diberikan begitu saja begitu efek vodka mulai terasa.	CP
This how you capitalize, this	Beginalah cara kamu memanfaatkannya, ini	SB, AD

is parental advised, and apparently, I'm over-influenced	<i>adalah konten dewasa, dan sepertinya, saya terlalu terpengaruh.</i>	
By what you are doin', I thought I was doin' the most 'til someone said to me	<i>Dari apa yang kamu lakukan, aku pikir aku yang paling hebat sampai ada yang bilang padaku</i>	AP
I ride, you ride, bang	<i>Aku turun, kamu turun dor!</i>	AD, SB
One chopper, one hundred shots, bang	<i>Satu senapan mesin, seratus tembakan, dor!</i>	AD, SB
Hop out, do you? bang	<i>Keluarlah, kamu mau? dor!</i>	AD, SB
Two chopper, two hundred shots, bang	<i>Dua senapan mesin, Dua ratus tembakan, dor!</i>	AD, SB
I ride, you ride, bang	<i>Aku turun, kamu turun, dor!</i>	AD, SB
One chopper, one hundred shots, bang	<i>Satu senapan mesin, seratus tembakan, tembak!</i>	AD
Hop out, do you bang?	<i>Keluarlah, Kamu mau? dor!</i>	AD, SB
two chopper, two hundred shots, bang	<i>Dua senapan mesin, Dua ratus tembakan, dor!</i>	AD, SB
Sherane	<i>Sherane</i>	LT
(Pool, Kendrick, Kendrick, lies in it, in, in, in)	<i>(Kolam, Kendrick, Kendrick, berada di dalamnya, di, di, di)</i>	LT
Sherane, Sherane	<i>Sherane, Sherane</i>	LT
(W-watch 'em all flock) Aw man	<i>(L-lihat mereka semua berkerumun) ya ampun!</i>	LT, AD
Sherane (Girls wanna play-play-play)	<i>Sherane (Para gadis ingin bermain-main-main)</i>	LT
Where is she takin' me? (I got)	<i>Kemana dia membawaku? (Aku dapat)</i>	LT
Where is she takin' me? (Pool full of liquor, I'ma die in it)	<i>Kemana dia membawaku? (Kolam penuh minuman keras, aku akan mati di dalamnya)</i>	LT
All I—all I—all I—	<i>Semua yang aku—semua yang aku—semua yang aku—</i>	LT
All I have in life is my new appetite for failure	<i>Satu-satunya yang kumiliki dalam hidup ini adalah hasrat baruku untuk menghadapi kegagalan.</i>	AP
And I got hunger pain that grow insane, tell me, do that sound familiar?	<i>Dan aku merasakan rasa lapar yang semakin tak tertahankan, katakanlah, apakah itu terdengar familiar bagimu?</i>	AP,

If it do, then you're like me, makin' excuse that your relief	<i>Jika iya, maka kamu seperti aku, mencari- cari alasan untuk meringankan bebanmu.</i>	AP, EQ
Is in the bottom of a bottle and the greenest indo leaf	<i>Ada di dasar botol dan daun ganja yang paling hijau.</i>	AD, PT
As the window open I release everything that corrode inside of me	<i>Saat jendela terbuka, aku melepaskan segala hal yang merusak di dalam diriku.</i>	LT
I see you jokin', why you laugh? Don't you feel bad? I prob'ly sleep	<i>Aku tahu kamu bercanda, kenapa kamu tertawa? apa kamu tidak merasa bersalah? Mungkin aku akan tidur.</i>	SB, PT
And never ever wake up, never ever wake up, never ever wake up	<i>dan jangan pernah bangun, jangan pernah bangun, jangan pernah bangun</i>	LT
In God I trust, but just when I thought I had enough	<i>Pada Tuhan aku percaya, tapi tepat ketika aku berpikir bahwa aku sudah cukup.</i>	LT
"They stomped the homie out over a bitch?	<i>"Mereka menghajar temannya habis-habisan karena seorang perempuan!"</i>	SB, GN
K-Dot, you good, blood?	<i>K-Dot, kamu baik-baik saja, bro?</i>	AD
"Now we can drop, yeah, we can drop you back off"	<i>"Sekarang kita bisa mengantar, ya, kita bisa mengantar kamu kembali."</i>	LT
"That nigga's straight, man, that nigga ain't trippin'"	<i>"Orang itu santai, bro, dia nggak ribet."</i>	AD
"We gon' do the same ol' shit	<i>"Kita akan melakukan hal yang sama seperti biasa."</i>	AD
I'ma pop a few shots, they gon' ru—they gon' run opposite way	<i>Akan aku tembak beberapa peluru, mereka akan lari—mereka akan lari ke arah berlawanan.</i>	AP
Fall right in ****'s lap	<i>Langsung jatuh ke pangkuan dia</i>	LT
And he gon' tear they ass up, simple as that"	<i>"Dan dia akan menghancurkan mereka, sesederhana itu."</i>	EQ
"And I hope that bitch that set him up, out there	<i>"Dan aku harap si jalang yang menjebakny, di luar sana. Kita juga akan menghajar si jalang itu."</i>	EQ, GN
We gon' pop that bitch too"		
"Wait hold up, ayy, I see some of 'em"	<i>"Tunggu dulu, ayo, aku lihat beberapa dari mereka"</i>	EQ, LT
"Aha! Got them niggas, K- Dot, you good?"	<i>"Aha! Sudah dapat mereka, K-Dot, kamu baik-baik saja?"</i>	EQ, AP
"L****, you good?"	<i>"Laurent, kamu baik-baik saja?"</i>	AD

"Yeah, bro, I'm good – D*****, you good? D*****? D*****? Say somethin' – D*****?"	<i>Yeah, bro, aku baik-baik saja – Dave, kamu baik-baik saja? Dave? Dave? Katakan sesuatu – Dave?</i>	AD, AP LT
These bitch-ass niggas killed my brother!"	<i>Para bajingan sialan itu membunuh saudaraku!"</i>	AD

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

In this chart, the author presents the translation methods that have been most frequently employed in the translations conducted.

Figure 1. Translation Chart

This study investigated the translation of Kendrick Lamar’s rap song “Swimming Pools (Drank) – Extended Version” into Indonesian, aiming to identify the most suitable translation methods using Molina & Albir’s framework. The discussion focuses on the consistent application of translation techniques and the rationale behind each choice, emphasizing both linguistic accuracy and cultural adaptation. The translation process began by verifying the lyrics with official sources and delving deeper into the artist’s background to ensure that every cultural nuance was understood. This step was vital to achieving not only literal accuracy but also authenticity in tone and intent.

Among the various techniques used in this study, adaptation emerges as the most effective translation technique for this rap song. Adaptation involves replacing cultural elements in the source text with culturally equivalent expressions in the target language, making the translation not only accurate in meaning but also relatable for Indonesian listeners. This is particularly crucial in rap songs, which are rich in cultural references, idioms, and slang that do not have direct equivalents in other languages.

Preserving Cultural Relevance: Adaptation allows potentially unfamiliar cultural references (such as those relating to American drinking culture or hip-hop slang) to be adjusted so they resonate with Indonesian audiences. For example, “babysittin’ only two or three shots” becomes “Cuma main dua atau tiga sloki aja,” preserving the metaphor’s meaning within a local context. **Maintaining Artistic Style:** Rhythm, rhyme, and flow are vital in rap. Adaptation enables the translator to reformulate phrases so they remain singable and impactful in Indonesian, avoiding awkward literal renderings that would disrupt the song’s musicality and energy. **Ensuring Acceptability:** By adapting emotionally charged or potentially offensive expressions (like the N-word), the translator promotes inclusivity and cultural appropriateness “Bro” is used instead, avoiding the original’s contentious term.

This report contrasts sharply with the journal (Utami & Satyaningrum, 2022) which argues that the most frequently used method in the Our Planet series is the establish equivalent method, as this method uses familiar TL terms or expressions. Modulation and description techniques, each with one data point (0.6%), were the least frequently used translation methods. This shows the contrast between the results of the report written by the author where the most widely used technique in translating this song is adaptation because this method adapts the culture from SL which is converted to TL. Therefore, it is also seen from the different translation subjects where the previous report translated the movie and the report made by the author translated the song so

that the most appropriate method can also be different.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings highlight that effective translation of rap lyrics requires not only linguistic competence but also creativity and deep cultural awareness. By carefully integrating adaptation with supporting techniques, the translation successfully maintained the essence, rhythm, and communicative function of the source text for Indonesian audiences. This research provides insights for students and practitioners of translation studies, especially those working with culturally rich texts such as music. The results are expected to contribute to a broader understanding of translation strategies and encourage more nuanced, culturally sensitive translations in future projects.

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